

SOCIO-CULTURAL REFLECTIONS IN SUFI LITERATURE OF BIHAR

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ABSTRACT

Sufism was mainly built upon the tentacles of Islam; it is a religion of love and brotherhood, as it stands for unity of mind and soul and works towards realization of self. It is not surprising therefore, that Sufism became a religion of teaming millions and had special appeal to both Muslims as well as the Hindus, in South Asia. Sufism found an amicable geographical and cultural abode throughout the length and breadth of the Indian subcontinent. Sufism and Sufi saints are an existing reality in socio-religious fold and have undoubtedly contributed immensely towards a healthy and amicable social order in India. Though its base was Islam, it followed the practice of humanism and therefore, became the religion of common people, because it appealed to their soul. Even for non-Muslims it presented a life of eternal freedom from the bondages of materialism to that of eternality and bliss. This Paper deals with the social and cultural scenario of Bihar as reflected in the writings of Sufis of Bihar.

Key Words: Socio-Cultural Reflections, Sufism, Bihar, Literature

INTRODUCTION

With the establishment of the Muslim rule in India after the Ghorian conquest, we find many people migrating to India from the middle-east, central Asia and Khurasan. Those included variety of people- Sufi saints, scholars, artists and scores of others who in search of better prospect of life came to India and settled here finding it a very suitable place for their livelihood and also extremely suitable for their spiritual quest. The huge Muslim migration or company by Muslim ulemas as well as Muslim mystics of varied silsilas impacted Islam in India. Mysticism had already become part of Islamic spirituality and great number of

followers had become associated with the mystic brand of Islamic spirituality. Sufism as it was known was very popular not only with the masses but Muslim elite (Umra-Susfa) and sometimes with the royalty.

Though not verified but it is claimed that the first Muslim saint was Khwaja Gharibnawaz who had already settled in India before the Ghorian conquest of Delhi and Ajmer. Along with him we find Sufi saints of repute one after another finding permanent home in India and having tremendous influence of Indian socio cultural aspects of society, some prominent Sufis being Baba Farid Gang-e- Shakar, Khwaja Nizamuddin Aulia, Khwaja Naseeruddin Chiragdelhi, Alishah Qalandera, Bakhtiyar Kaki and scores of others.

As for the contribution of the Sufi movements of India, it is almost an established fact is that the Sufi saints of various shades had greatly contributed in the evolution of medieval composite society.

In medieval India, Islam was extremely new to the Indian masses and Islam was not easily finding the assimilation and some extra effort needed by the Sufi saints to work as a bridge between the faithful of great religions, Hindus and Muslims. The Sufi saints of medieval period had universal appeal for all the Sects, castes creed and people of different spirituality and doors were open for everyone. The chief message involved was humanity, brotherhood and service to humanity. So much so that the Sufi Khanqahs became centre of great attraction for all. The Khanqahs were flocked by poor, destitute, widows and orphans along with the nobles, elites and royalty alike. Thus we find that the message reached to the common message of love without any discrimination. We find great many references of Hindus becoming disciples of Muslim Sufi saints and also spreading harmony of living together.

The Sufis contribution in regard to the socio-cultural aspects is also to be explored in terms of the development of literature during the early medieval period. Sufis not only were spiritual men but also were great literary figures. They produced marvelous literature during medieval period and enriched the Persian, Arabic and Hindi literature during the whole of medieval period. As for the contribution in the development of Hindi literature is concerned we find that with the efforts of the Sufis almost new style of literature developed which had emerged with the mixture of Persian with local Indian dialects. The Khanqahs became a

centre of such spoken language which was understood by all and the Sufi saints like Baba Farid, Khwaja Nizamuddin Aulia, Amir Khusrau, Abdul Quddus Grgohi and others greatly contributed in the development of such literature both in prose and poetry using hindvi as dialect. We find a number of Dohas, Sakhois and other kinds of love poems which came to be known as Prem Akhyan literature being developed by the Sufi saints.

The literature which is a result of Sufi discourses also played a vital role in the development of literature of the medieval period. The literature in the form of Malfuzat, Maktubat and live biographies of Sufis apart from their poetics, provide us with a plethora of literatures like the famous Malfuzat of Shaikh Nizamuddin Aulia and others. Such literature is treasure of socio-cultural study of medieval period. The same literature is a reflection of social, political, economic and cultural aspect of 13th to 14th century of north Indian society.

Thus we find that from the literature there is information about the existing political condition and the activities of the royalty from the literatures. The other aspects of lie can also be found from the Sufi literature and we can reconstruct the history of past society taking help from the Sufi Malfuzat.

The contribution also can be enumerated from the fact that the Sufis are also lovers of music (Sama) the Sama became part of Sufi gathering at a time of the anniversary of the deadly saints. That led to the development to the musical styles and vocal traditions in which the writings of Sufi saints were sung and orally presented to the audience, Amir khusrau, the great disciple of Nizamuddin Aulia inventing various ragas, khyals, and Shailies. He also wrote a number of Qawwalis and Ghazliat which consisted of love themes and transcending spirituality.

Keeping in mind the above scenario of North India during 13th to 14th century, we can also study the same aspect in context of Bihar which during the time was under the control of Sultans of Bengal. The Sufis of Bihar had become very popular among the masses during 14th century not by dint of their writings and discourses but also through their mystical gatherings, teachings of universal brotherhood, love and service to humanity. The literature which they produced reflects all the above features and provides us with all kinds of

information which deals with the social harmony, amalgamation of various castes and creeds along with helping the poor. Khanqahs were an excellent example of this intermixing of people who belonged to different faiths.

The contribution of prominent Sufis of Bihar, particularly the Firdausi Sufi saint Shaikh Sharfuddin Yahya Maneri is unparalleled and he is greatly admired, loved and revered by the people of Bihar and Bengal during Sultanate period and continued to be respected and followed for centuries and even at present.

The influence of Sufism cut across the barriers of religions and castes. To cite just one example, in Mehsi town of East Champaran district, the Dargah of Halim Shah is revered by both Hindus and Muslims. This shrine predates the establishment of Muslim rule over the district. At the entrance is the Samadhi of Mahesh, the chief disciple of Halim Shah, who did not convert to Islam and, according to popular belief, as per the mandate of Halim Shah, people entering the Dargah have to offer floral tributes first to Mahesh. The town is named after him. Such shrines are scattered throughout Bihar in dozens. As is common knowledge, both the communities took part in each other's religious festivals with great devotion and enthusiasm (*Identity and politics in Eastern India, Newsdesk, March 23, 2009.*)

Prominent Sufis of Bihar

Many Sufi orders of good repute, the Chistiya, Suharwardia, Firdausia, Qadriya and Madariya, were represented in Bihar, and each one had contributed in the spread and development of Islam. Among the earliest to come were the Sufis of Chistiya order. Some of the renowned names of this order being Shah Mahmud Bihari and Saiyad Taju-ddin of Danapur, the disciples of Qutbuddin Bakhtiyar Kaki, Maulana 'Ali Bihari, a disciple of Baba Farid Ganj-i-Shakar, Makhdum Adam Sufi, son of Saiyid Ibrahim Chisti of what later became Hajipur, and his son Makhdum Hamidu'd Din and the latter's son Taimullah Sufaid Baz, the spiritual guide of Shaikh Faidullah of Kurgi near Patna, Shamsud' Din of Chanda's (Biharsharif). Taimullah Sufaid Baz had settled down in mahalla Chistiana of Biharsharif which was adjacent to mahalla Bhasasur where lie buried a large number of Chisti saints, including Ahmad 'Isa Taj, the younger brother of the celebrated Chisti saint, Muhammad 'Isa Taj, a son-in-law of Saiyid Jalal Bukhari Makhdum Jahaniyan of Suharwardi order.

Some prominent Sufis of Suharwardi order were Shaikh Jalal Tabrizi, one of the chief disciples of the celebrated author of 'Awarifu'l-Ma'arif, Shihabu'd Din Suharwardi, came to Bihar via Delhi and Badaun and from there he went to Bengal and Sylhet where his Chilla Khana is still found. He has been mentioned by Makhdum Sharaful Din and his discourses. Maulana Ahmad Damishq, one of the Khalifas of the celebrated Bahaud' Din Zakariya Multani was the spiritual guide of Maulana Taqlu'd Din Suharwardi of Mahsun (Dinajpur, Bengal) the author of Multaqit which is an abridged version of Ghazza's Ihyau'l 'ULum, Taqlu'd Din was the inspirer of many Suharwardi saints of Bihar, including Makhdum Yahya Maneri, the father of the celebrated Firdausi saint, Makhdum Sharfuddin Maneri.

Sheikh Sharfuddin was liberal and broad-minded in his approach towards the non-muslims. In his discourses and letters he quotes with approval from the great mystic 'Ainu'l Quddat Hamasdani who had profound admiration for the founders of all religions who formed their views on the basis of religious experiences. Their followers failed to grasp the real significance of the original teachings and turned their meanings. When asked about the yogi who said that one who wished to live should know how to die, the Shaikh said that they did say so but did not believe in true significance. Ignorant transmitters missed the deep religious spirit behind such statements. Referring to Islam, the Shaikh said that it came in all perfection, but its commands were not observed and there had been deviation from its original ideology. He also had unstinted admiration for the supreme expression of love for Hindus, convinced through self-immolation which he had witnessed on several occasions in Raigir. He tells us of a man who had killed himself when a stone image he had in his left hand fell down. He had been standing on one leg, and his nails had grown so long as to be entwined around his hand. It is love which inspired his action. There are references to widowed women who had abandoned the world and took recourse to self-immolation by setting fire to their clothes soaked in naphtha oil. Such emotional ascetic practices evoked keen appreciation but not commendation from the saint of Maner. Genuine asceticism, according to the saint, results in great liberty and the purification of the soul, and this liberty can be acquired either by a believer or an infidel.

Sufis relationship with the Kings and Nobles:

The Firdausi saints were indifferent towards politics and shunned all connections with royalty and men of noble rank and position. However the Suharwardia and Shuttaria Sufis did not abstain from all kinds of associations with Kings and Nobles and felt no scruples in accepting not only such ecclesiastical jobs as those of the almoner but even Jagirs and favours which they used for the benefit of the people. They held that high position does not do harm to those who know its antidote. The well-known Suharwardia saint, Saiyid Jalal Bukhari was held in high esteem not only by the greatest saint of Bihar but also by emperor Firuz Tughlaq, and his capable wazir, Khan-i-Jahan Maqbul. Powerful governors like Ainul Mulk and displaced rulers of Sindh, like Jam Khairuddin Jam and Jan Babinia sought his intercession. He used to come very often to Delhi and his recommendations for favours for the poor and the needy was always accepted by the king.

Maneri's Makhtubat contains letters written in reply to emperors such as Muhammad Tughlaq and Firoz Shah Tughlaq, princes such as Dawar Malik, governors such as Mufarrihul Mulk and Hesamud Din and officials and nobles too numerous to mention. The learned Maulana Muzafar Shams Balkhi who had given up his job in Firuz Sha's Arabic college, situated in Kushak-i-Lal at Delhi to become the disciple of the great saint of Bihar, was as puritanical in his outlook as to shun all worldly things and give away in charity even his books. He tied his Izar or close fitted trouser with a 'munj' string and gave up even his wife, divorcing her and himself arranging her marriage with another, lest his growing affection towards her should affect his devotion to God. Yet, he was also on terms of correspondence with Sultan Ghyasuddin of Bengal. Ten of his letters, addressed to Sultan, relating mostly on religious matters are found in a voluminous work left by him. Thus, these saints had no aversion towards rulers and men in power and recognized the utility of their high offices and position. Yet, they would never bow before them, nor would accept anything from their hands. According to the letters of Maneri written to Muhammad Dawar Malik(son-in-law) of Muhammad Bin Tughlaq, he would recommend genuine cases of poverty and piety for favour and help. But he would have nothing for himself and in his admonitions to kings and officials he was quite frank and did not mince matters (*Muhammad, Y.T. Sufi movement in Eastern India, Anmol publication, Delhi, Pg.68.*)

According to Munisu'l Qulab, when emperor Muhammad Bin Tughlaq learnt that on the entreaties of his followers the great saint of Bihar had condescended to descend from the Rajgir hills and traveled on foot every week to Biharsharif, he sent a Bulgarian prayer carpet as a present and ordered Zainu'd Din Majdu'l Mulk, the governor of Bihar to bestow something from Rajgir as a jagir for the upkeep of the Khanqah which had to be built for the saint of Biharsharif. The saint would not accept Jagir and he preferred to deliver his sermons by sitting under the "Do Chapra" Nizamud Din Maula had set up for his weekly sermons out of his legitimately earned money or Mal-i-muzakka. He had however to relent on the personal entreaties of the governor who told him what he was likely to expect from the despotic Sultan if his orders were not carried out. It is not a fact, as stated in Munisu'l Qulub, that he had to undertake the strenuous journey to Delhi, where he arrived after the death of the Sultan and the deed of the Jagir was returned to his successor, Firuz Shah Tughlaq. It was only once that he went to Delhi, and the Jagir was returned fifteen years later to Firuz Shah when he, on his way to Bengal in A.H.754, stopped in Bihar and paid a visit to the great saint. This valuable information is found in The Maktubat of Hasan Mu'iz Balkhi, and we can infer the date of establishment of the Khanqah (754) from it (*Askari, S.H. Islam and Bihar, Pg.114.*)

Socio Cultural significance

The Sufi literature available throws some light on the relations between the Sufis, on the one hand, and the court, the different Muslim social groups, ascetics and non-Muslims and also lower classes of people that surrounded them.

In Sufistic literature it is rare that we come across people such as chakars, nafar (servants, attendants), parah doz (tailors) and na'lain doz (shoemakers, etc). In his commentary on Abab, Makhdum Sirajuddin refers, besides Kushawaran, (agriculturist) and Ahl-i-Hirfa (artisans) to many type of workers such as carpenters, workers in leather, carriers of burden, tailors, sack makers, fullers, bootmakers, spindle makers, blacksmiths, barbers etc. These earned bread by lawful means and had catered to the needs of mankind since olden times. The saint condemned beggary and advocated kasb(earning), or the conception of vocation or calling, that is doing manfully the work to earn bread for himself and his family and not to accumulate

wealth. Kasb or labour for earning bare necessities of life was substituted for the old ascetic ideal of renunciation of the world. Kasb was an indispensable precept (fardiat), but with conditional conjunction of necessity. There should be no hoarding and the means must be lawful.

As practical people, the Sufis dealt realistically and sensible with every-day works and activities of the labourers, poor women and pious persons earning their bread by hard work, and also honest men urged by the prompting of sex. The Kanizgan (slave-girls) who had to soil their hands and feet with dirt and mud when they thronged round the wells to draw water could not be expected to complete purificatory wash before sitting down to cook and eat their food. Workers in the field and labourers who came barefooted were allowed by the Prophet to enter and offer their prayers in the mosque. Impurity did not lie in the dust trodden by the feet, or fatwa or religious decree about such dirt and nastiness would be oppressive to many people. Maulana Muzzaffar was very glad to know that his disciple in Bengal, Khwaja Hamia (*Maktubat-i-Muzafar Shams Balkhi., Khudabaksh Library, Patna*) had at least performed Nikah which was a divine command. He had advised a disciple to purchase a slave-girl (jaria) as to avoid sins.

The Sufis often quoted the two dicta of the Prophet; “Give to men what were rights”, and “place men in their proper ranks”, and Makhdum Sharfuddin cited an instance of different ways in which Ayesha, the Prophet’s wife, received a simple believer and a Muhtasham (*Tuhfa-i-Ghaibi, Quoted in Askari, Pg.112*) and he said that, “some rose to be rulers, some wazirs and high official, khan, Maliks, “Alim, yet the people of lower orders had also their role to play what would happen if this city becomes denuded of Naddafs (cotton dressers). This shows unawareness about the importance of the artisan class. The Sufis thought that the relation between members and society was with reference to the sphere of action and it was one of social existence.

Sufism had provided many opportunities for women to give themselves up to a life of devotion and some had attained a state of conscious spirituality, perhaps far ahead of male members. But it was not permissible for them to assume the position of a religious guide or Pir, and initiate a neophyte by the usual method of giving or placing hand on hand (dast bar

dast) in compact, cutting a few hairs of his head with scissors, giving a khirqā, a taquia and a shaira. In this connection, a letter of the 15th century saint Abdul Quddus Gangohi addressed to a pious talented Afghan lady, Bubu Khatun (*Maktubat-i-Quddusiya, Discourses of Makhdum Maneri, Khudabaksh Library, Patna*) found in his Maktubat forms interesting reading.

One Makhdum Sharfuddin observed that the things which are prescribed in law include what is done as a habit for love of wife and children. But he warns that some women were rahbar (guide) while others were rahbur (highway robber), the former encouraging and helping their husbands to pursue the path of truth, devotion and submission, and the latter intercepting the road to truth and leading the husbands astray from the right way. There might be Khula in the case of the latter, setting them free or resigning the marriage settlement, as was Talaq, permissible for men.

Sufis and social service:

The Sufis especially of the Firdausia order, were large hearted and gentle in their views and very liberal in their attitudes, of sympathy and understanding. There are many references to their written recommendations for help to the poor and deserving people to the kings and nobles. They would not accept jobs and jagirs from the high and the mighty, but would go out of the way to help the poor and never ignored them. It would suffice to refer to the letter which the Makhdum wrote to Firuz shah tughlaq and to Malik Mufarrih and to the many letters of the Makhdum Balkhi successor, Muzzafar Shams Balkhi, calling the attention of the officials and nobles of Bengal to the plight of Darwesh like businessmen fallen on evil days who would never open their lips before others. In the Khwani-i-pur Ni'mat (*Khwan-i Pur Ni'mat Quoted in Askari, Pg.112*) we find the Makhdum saying, "when I was in my old cell (apparently Rajgir) the ruler of the place was a Malik, and the poor and indigent of the region pestered me so much that I began to feel tired of writing papers of recommendations. He was however reminded by a Shaikhzada of Chisti of his great ancestor, Khwaja Maudud Chisti, who despite repeated repulsions and humiliations continued to approach even personally the ruler of the area for redressal of grievances and rendering help to needy ones. The Ganj-i-la-

Yakhfa (*Ganj-i-La-Yakhfa, Khudabaksh Libarray, Patna*) of Husain Mui'z Balkhi records that among those who attended the 18th majlis there were Malik Badh Kotwal and Saiyid Saiyidu's Sadat, the Katib (official, secretary). Addressing them, the Balkhi saint that a hindu had come and complained that the authorities of the Diwani were demanding from him rusum (custom duties or taxes) which he had not been called upon to pay at any time. He asked them to give him relief and protection, and exempt him from new demands. He observed that infidelity and faith, orthodoxy and heresy, were technical terms and should not be stretched to apply to men of religions, sects and schisms and did not come against care and consideration. There is no real enmity in anything and against anybody. Profane or superficial enmity was largely occasioned by selfish desires and interests. He cited the traditions about Prophet Moses who was warned up by God for not responding to the call for help from a repentant Pharaoh when he was in a drowning stage and about Prophet Abraham for denying shelter to a creature of God on the ground of being non-believer.

Thus we find that Sufi Literature produced in Bihar is of great significance in terms of the socio cultural study of medieval times. A number of Malfuzat and Maktubats were produced in Bihar and their study gives a good insight into the historical and socio-cultural life of that part of India.

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